

ABSTRACT

FBA and generalized Lotka-Volterra integration for microbial community modeling

Iha, B. K. V.¹; Setubal, J. C.¹; Stadler, P. F.².

¹Department of Biochemistry, Institute of Chemistry, University of São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil; ²Fakultät für Mathematik und Informatik, Universität Leipzig, Leipzig, Germany.

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The study of the behavior and dynamics of microbial communities constitutes a big challenge due to the complex metabolisms and interspecies interactions present. This led to the creation of multiple computational models in the hopes of shedding light on this topic. The most commonly used models are based on two different methods: the generic Lotka-Volterra (gLV) and Flux Balance Analysis (FBA). gLV is a simple model based on differential equations that only requires a small set of fixed parameters. The simplicity of this method makes it easy to interpret but at the same time severely limits the representation of complex systems. Several adaptations were proposed to represent some complex mechanisms (cross-feeding, growth saturation, physico-chemical variables, etc), but due to the limited knowledge this method still remains an overly simplification of reality. In contrast to gLV, FBA uses the knowledge we have about metabolic pathways and the environmental compounds to calculate the possible metabolic fluxes and use it to predict the behavior of a microbe. But because there is not much clear data on inter-species metabolic interactions most cases of interactions between bacteria are not predictable. This was addressed with several additions to FBA based methods (game theory, stochastics, multi-objective optimization, etc) but those additions still deal with microbial interactions in indirect ways. It is noticeable that the advantages of each method complement the limitations of the other. In this work gLV and FBA were adapted to work together in synergy in a model so that the metabolic simulation of FBA will complement the lack of metabolic information in gLV and the simple, yet effective, representation of inter-species interaction of gLV will compensate for the lack of information in FBA. This model is able to identify correlation between reactions and metabolites and interactions between species.

Keywords: Microbiology; Modeling; Metabolic Analysis.

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